

4D PRINTED PROGRAMMABLE STRUCTURES BASE ON ACTIVE SHAPE MEMORY POLYMER COMPOSITES

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Keywords: 4D printing, Shape Memory Polymer, Programmable, Cellular structure, Bio-robot

ABSTRACT

The advances of multi-material 3D printing technology have enabled the creation of multi-material composites with complex configurations. And Shape Memory Polymers (SMPs) as a kind of intriguing functional materials have been widely applied to various active structures and 4D Printing. In this study, via commercial duo-material Fused Deposition Modeling (FDM) technology, multi-layer SMP structures were combined with elastomeric matrix to develop a set of 4D printed active programmable composites and structures with diverse functions, such as diverse deformation patterns, tuneable mechanical properties and the time-programmable bi-stable transition behaviour. According to that, three programming methods based on external loads, internal pre-strain and viscoelasticity were presented and investigated here.

1 INTRODUCTION

Firstly, in this paper, based on shape memory effect and composite anisotropy, we developed a variety of structures programmable with simple external loads, which including adaptable composites with diverse deformation patterns (bending, curling, twisting and folding) and programmable cellular structures with tuneable mechanical properties (Poisson ratio, chirality, anisotropy and out-plane configurations). Then, utilizing the pre-strain during printing, active self-deformable structures with variable curvature were realized without external loading. Moreover, a time-programmable bi-stable structure was achieved based on the shape memory effect and viscoelasticity. An adaptable turbine prototype and a bionic time-programmable jumping robot were proposed and fabricated to demonstrate their potential applicability.

With those adjustable properties mentioned above, programmable structures can be widely applied to deployable structures, self-assembly devices, soft robotics, auto-packaging and wearable devices.

2 EXTERNAL SIMPLE LOADS PROGRAMMABLE 4D PRINTED STRUCTURES

2.1 Programmable Shape Memory Polymer Composites (SMPCs)

In active structures, SMPs usually serve as active materials, and soft [1-3] or rigid [4, 5] materials act as matrix materials to provide an antagonistic effect. In this work, three dimensional structures of multi-layer Polylactic Acid (PLA) with shape memory effect were involved as the active phase, and Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU) elastomer was utilized as the antagonistic phase.

Multi-layer 3D structures of SMP were embed in the matrix of the elastomer with chosen locations, thickness, and orientations. 3D structures of SMP and elastic matrix interlocks mutually with each other to prevent the detachment. The composites were activated by heating up to a point above the transition temperature and uniaxial or multi-axial tension loading, then cooling down to the room temperature and releasing the load (Fig.1). With the above steps, a variety of deformation including bending, curling and twisting were realized with the active composites (Fig.2).

Base on the classical composite material theory, with diverse selected locations, thickness and orientations, after activated the composites can generate various deformation patterns due to the mismatch between the active phase and antagonistic phase, as (Fig.1&2). Moreover, the third phase of blank can also be involved by 3D printing, which brings more room for creativity and were utilized in the twisting pattern of this study.

2.1 Programmable Cellular Structures with Tunable Mechanical Properties

Programmable or tunable cellular structures can bring more adaptability to materials [5-7]. In this study, the programmable SMPC was utilized to enable the tunable properties of cellular structures such as programmable out-plane configurations (Fig.3), Poisson ratio, chirality and anisotropy (Fig.3&4).

By applying the active composites to specific cellular structures with different arrangements, the poison ratio, chirality, anisotropy and out-plane configuration can be programmed by the combined effect of thermal and mechanical loads. In this study, a set of programmable cellular structures were fabricated via duo-material 3D printer to demonstrated the concepts of tunable poison ratio, chirality, anisotropy and out-plane configuration severally or jointly.

Fig.3 A 2D cellular structure with tilted walls transformed to a 3D anti-chiral convex structure.

Fig.4 Cellular structures with tunable Poisson ratio from positive to negative (a) and tunable anti-chirality (b).

3 INTERNAL PRE-STRAIN PROGRAMMING

3.1 Pre-programmable Structures with Variable Curvature

In this part, the printing conditions were adjusted particularly and carefully to induce the pre-strain of the shape memory PLA as the driving source of self-deformation [8]. A set of variable curvature surface structures activatable by heating were achieved and presented to clarify the design principles of self-deforming structures (Fig.5). And a mini prototype of adaptable turbine blades was developed and verified (Fig.6).

4 A Bionic Time-programmable Bi-stable Structure Imitating the Click Beetle

A variable bi-stable structure was involved by thermal shape memory effect and pre-strain (Fig.7a, b& d). And due to the viscoelasticity and residual strain of TPU layers, the time-dependent bi-stable state transition and jumping were introduced by the stress relaxation during and after pressing on the structure (Fig.7c), where the longer t_1 is, the longer t_2 is required (Fig.7b-e) and when t_1 is long enough, the transition from state1 to state2 would be irreversible.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Via multi-material 3D printing technology, SMP structures can be combined with elastomeric matrix to develop a set of 4D printed active programmable composites and structures with diverse deformation patterns, tuneable mechanical properties and the time-programmable bi-stable transition behaviour. Based on these adjustable properties, programmable structures can bring more functions to the raw materials or structures.

Three programming methods based on external loads, internal pre-strain and viscoelasticity were presented and investigated in this study. Firstly, interlocked 3D structures of SMP and matrix not only bring a feasible method to reprogram the shape of materials or structures and modify their mechanical properties, but also prevent the detachment between the two phases with much difference in stiffness. Secondly, internal pre-strain can achieve a self-drive deformation under outside stimuli, which enable devices to realize the self-adaptive capability to environmental conditions. Moreover, the time-programmable behaviour based on the intrinsic time-dependent property of viscoelastic material, which presents a more feasible programming performance and short-term memory effect, comparing with SMP. This effect will be more useful in sequential logical programming.

Three programming methods of 4D SMP composites will bring more possibility to the design of active structures in the field of MEMS (micro electro mechanical system), self-assembly, soft robotics and wearable devices.

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